

THE POLITICAL ECONOMY OF BANDITRY AND ITS IMPACT ON INTER-GROUP HARMONY: THE NIGERIAN EXPERIENCE, 2011–2025

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Abstract:

Banditry in Nigeria has evolved from a localised rural criminal network into a complex political economy that has essentially impacted on inter-group harmony in Nigeria, particularly in the North-West and North-Central geopolitical zones. This paper, examined the political economy of banditry and its implications on inter group relations in Nigeria from 2011 and 2025. The study, based on a qualitative research design, and grounded in both primary and secondary data, examined the structural factors behind banditry such as elite predation, competition over natural resources, unemployment, poor governance, and proliferation of small arms. The study employed the use of the Relative Deprivation Theory and the Political Economy Theory as frameworks for analysis. Findings revealed that banditry has metamorphosed into a well-organised criminal enterprise sustained by ransom economies, illicit arms trade, and cattle rustling networks, which in turn has impacted on inter-ethnic and inter-religious relations among the Hausa, Fulani, Gwari, Kadara, and other communities. The study established that a breakdown in trust between herding and farming communities has led to increased violence, displacement, and food insecurity in the region, and Nigeria as a whole. It recommended the implementation of effective community-based conflict resolution processes, equal resource distribution, economic empowerment for youths, inter-community communication systems, and improved security governance. The study concluded that sustainable intergroup harmony must address the structural origins of banditry rather than depending solely on selective military approaches.

Introduction

Nigeria's security landscape has changed significantly and alarmingly since the early

2010s. Previously restricted to small-scale brigandage and livestock rustling, banditry, has developed into a well-organized business with a

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substantial political economy. Criminal elements operating in the states of Katsina, Kebbi, Sokoto, Zamfara, Kaduna, and Niger have increased the scope of their operations to include the illegal trafficking of small arms and light weapons (SALWs), attacks on military formations, sacking of farming communities, and mass kidnapping for ransom. The volume and sophistication of these activities have prompted some analysts to characterise contemporary banditry not as mere criminality but as a form of insurgency with structural roots in Nigeria's long-history of governance deficit (Olaniyan & Yahaya, 2016).

The period 2011-2025 are significantly important. The year 2011 marked the escalation of the Boko Haram insurgency in the North-East that pulled state security resources to the East and inadvertently left power vacuum in the North-West and North-Central areas where banditry found renewed vigor. By 2014, cattle rustling had turned into multi-billion-naira criminal economy (Adibe, 2014). Between 2019-2023, the number of deaths associated with banditry surpassed those associated with the Boko Haram conflict in certain years, indicating a drastic increase (Amnesty International, 2025). The emergence of the President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's administration in 2023 was met with renewed hope, however, his government has continued to struggle with the menace, with military actions yielding little or no results.

Central to this study, nonetheless, are the effects of banditry on inter-group harmony in Nigeria. Nigeria's multi-ethnic and multi-religious character makes it particularly susceptible to the

instrumentality of violence along identity lines. As bandit groups (though predominantly but not exclusively Fulani) raid farming communities, the violence has increasingly acquired ethnic and religious colourations, straining historically co-operative relations between communal groups. This study, therefore, examined the political economy of banditry and its implications for inter-group harmony in Nigeria from 2011 to 2025.

Statement of the Problem

Although the literature on insecurity in Nigeria is growing, the political economy aspects of banditry and its particular effect on inter-group harmony have not been adequately theorised. The majority of current literature assume banditry as a security issue that needs to be addressed by military actions without sufficiently questioning the structural economic and political aspects that produces and fuels it. This analytical gap is important since incorrect diagnosis is followed by policy prescriptions that addresses symptoms, not the causes. The issue is further aggravated by the fact that banditry does not exist in a vacuum. It is entrenched in a political economy that is marked by elite capture of the state resources, patronage networks that at times infiltrate into protection of criminal gangs, land tenure wars that are enhanced by climate change, and a youth unemployment crisis. Such structural determinants are combined with Nigeria heavily fragmented social fabric to generate violence which has habitual ethnic, religious, and communal boundaries. Furthermore, the Nigerian government's response to banditry has been inconsistent, alternating between military raids,

negotiated amnesties, and outright disregard. The amnesty given to some bandit leaders in Zamfara between 2019 and 2021 was harshly criticized for legitimizing criminal activity without addressing the underlying grievances. Thus, this paper poses the following questions: What are the political economy factors behind banditry in Nigeria? What has been the impact of banditry on intergroup harmony among impacted communities? What policy interventions can foster lasting peace? It is the desire to give meaning to these questions that this study became inevitable.

Methodology

This study is qualitative in nature. It utilized data derived from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data source includes oral interviews with knowledgeable stakeholders (both within and outside of the North West and North Central), while secondary data was derived mainly from academic journal articles, government reports, and human rights documentation from organizations such as Amnesty International, and other reliable media sources. Thematic analysis was used to analyse the data, and common themes such as drivers of political economy, inter-group relations, state response and policy implications were used as organising categories. The triangulation of several secondary sources offered a strong empirical basis to the argument and conclusions of the study.

Definition of Terms

Banditry: For the purpose of this study, banditry is conceived as organised armed criminality that includes cattle rustling, kidnapping for ransom, armed robbery,

destruction of farmland, and attacks on communities and security forces. It is distinguished from Boko Haram-style jihadist insurgency by its primarily economic (rather than ideological) motivation, though the boundaries between these categories have increasingly blurred (Olaniyan & Yahaya, 2016). **Political Economy:** Political economy is used to refer to the association between political authority, economic systems and social consequences. It highlights the role of resource distribution, interests of elite, forms of governance and relations of classes in the creation and maintenance of violence (Keen, 1998).

Inter-group Harmony: Inter-group harmony is a state of peaceful co-existence, cooperation and mutual tolerance between separate ethnic, religious or occupational groups of people occupying geographic or social space. It involves both formal and informal conflict management strategies which govern inter-community relationships (Nnoli, 1978).

Small Arms and Light Weapons (SALWs): SALWs are personal or small group weapons, such as assault weapons, pistols, rocket-propelled grenades and light machine guns. A key facilitator of banditry activities in the Sahel and in the northern parts of Nigeria is their proliferation (ECOWAS, 2006).

Theoretical Framework

The present research is based on two complementary theoretical models; the Political Economy Theory and Relative Deprivation Theory.

Political Economy Theory

The political economy approach to conflict, which has been identified with the likes of David Keen (1998), Paul Collier and Anke Hoeffler (2004) assumes that wars and organised violence are not simply products of grievance, but are also shaped by greed and the rational pursuit of economic benefit. Keen's seminal study on the *Economic Functions of Violence* argues that combatants may have cogent motivations for prolonging conflict, as war creates opportunities for looting, extortion, and resource capture that would be inaccessible in peacetime. Applied to the study, the political economy paradigm directs attention to the ransom economy (estimated by Usman (2026) at over ₦1 trillion between 2016 and 2021), the cattle rustling trade, and the illicit arms markets that sustain bandit groups as economic enterprises. It also illuminates the role of political elites who may benefit from instability or who use security budgets as patronage resources without effectively deploying them against armed groups (International Crisis Group, 2020).

Relative Deprivation Theory

According to Relative Depravity Theory, which was developed by criminologists Stephen Schafer (1974) and Robert Agnew (1992) under general strain theory, when legitimate avenues for advancement are blocked by state failure and unequal resource distribution, aggrieved groups rationalize banditry as a compensatory or retaliatory mechanism. This theory, when applied to Nigeria, explains how the political economy of banditry—which is marked by the state's coercive extraction without redistributive justice, elite capture of oil revenues, and

widespread youth unemployment—fuel cattle rustling, kidnapping, and armed militias in the North-West and Middle Belt, which in turn undermines intergroup harmony by escalating ethnic and religious scapegoating, vigilante retaliation, and mistrust.

Historical Antecedents and the Trajectory of Banditry

Historically, northern Nigeria has a long history of banditry. Scholars, for decades, have traced the roots of this menace to colonial-era intercommunal conflicts over cattle rustling and grazing routes (Adibe, 2014). During this period and in the 1970s, indigenous establishments like the *Miyetti Allah* (Fulani pastoralists' association) and *Jangali* (cattle taxes) handled cattle rustling and intercommunal resource disputes, ensuring reparations without widespread violence (Adesoji, 2010). Nonetheless, the post-2011 period saw a rupture that differed qualitatively in terms of scale, organization, armament, and sociopolitical influence. Several factors contributed to this.

The first antecedent is environmental. The shrinking of Lake Chad and subsequent desertification, forced pastoralists southwards, intensifying farmer-herder clashes. In the Northwest, states like Zamfara and Katsina (once buffer zones) became epicenters of competition over land and water (Okoli & Okpaleke, 2014). Second, the collapse of Muammar Gaddafi's dictatorship in Libya in 2011 brought trained warriors and sophisticated weapons to the Sahel region, including Nigeria's northern zones (International Crisis Group, 2020). Third, the Nigerian government's heavy concentration on combatting Boko Haram in the

North East resulted in security gaps in the North West, allowing bandit networks to coalesce. Fourth, the destabilization of the traditional institution of the Hisba (Islamic social regulators) and the deterioration of Emirate power undermined informal governance and conflict management systems that in the past mediated between communities (Wani, 2015).

By 2014, Zamfara State had become the epicenter of cattle rustling pandemic, which the Nigerian government admitted had killed thousands and displaced hundreds of thousands (Hassani, 2026). The emergence of prominent bandit warlords like Bello Turji, Dogo Gide, and Kachalla (who commanded thousands of fighters and governed de facto criminal fiefdoms) signaled the shift from episodic criminality to structured armed activity (International Crisis Group, 2020).

The Political Economy of Banditry

The political economy of modern-day banditry in Nigeria functions on a number of interconnected levels. At the primary level is – ransom economy. Bandit groups have made enormous wealth from the widespread abduction of tourists, farmers, and school children. The kidnappings of 279 students from Government Girls Secondary School in Jangebe in February 2021 and 344 students from Government Science Secondary School in Kankara in December 2020 drew attention from around the world to a situation that local actors had been recording since at least 2014 (Amnesty International, 2025; Samuel & Omojo, 2025).

Although estimates of the ransom economy vary, scholars and security experts have indicated that bandit groups earned hundreds of

millions of naira per month from abduction operations during the crisis's peak from 2019 to 2022. According to Usman (2026), this wealth was utilized to purchase superior weapons, such as anti-aircraft guns and armored vehicles, as well as develop ties with politically connected figures.

Furthermore, cattle rustling remains a significant component of the banditry economy. Nigeria has one of Africa's largest cattle herds, and cattle theft costs the economy billions of naira each year. Rustled cattle are laundered through informal marketplaces in Nigeria, Niger, and the Benin Republic, producing funds to support bandit operations and simplifying arms purchase (Samuel & Omojo, 2025).

The political aspects of the economy require special consideration. Several investigative reports and academic analyses have discovered that political and business elites, such as arms dealers, local government officials, and traditional rulers, provide protection, intelligence, and logistical support to criminal networks in exchange for a cut of the profits (International Crisis Group, 2020; Human Rights Watch, 2021). Conventional military operations have had limited success due to the elite's control over the banditry economy, which includes the mechanisms created to combat it.

Banditry and the Fracturing of Inter-group Harmony

The impact of banditry on inter-group harmony is likely the most severe and long-lasting aspect of the problem. The North-West of Nigeria is distinguished by a historically complex but frequently coexisting tapestry of ethnic and occupational groups (Kadara, Hausa farmers,

Gwari, Fulani herders, Kamuku, and others) whose relationships were governed by traditional institutions, shared religious norms, and customary land and water use agreements (Nnoli, 1978; Aloko, 2025). The emergence of banditry has gradually eroded these coexisting systems. As bandit groups (mainly but not totally of Fulani origin) raid farming communities, killing farmers and destroying crops, ethnic identities are weaponized in a way that blurs the distinction between bandit violence and communal conflict. Farming communities in Zamfara, Katsina, and southern Kaduna increasingly perceive all Fulani herders as potential threats, while herders feel collectively stigmatized by the criminal activities of armed minorities (Nwakanma & Aina 2023; Usman, 2026).

Furthermore, the recurring cycle of attack and retaliation has resulted in what conflict scholars refer to as "security dilemma" dynamics (as one group equips itself for self-defense, others see an offensive threat and follow suit), intensifying violence beyond the initial crime-community context into full-scale inter-communal war (Fearon & Laitin, 1996). This dynamic is best illustrated by the phenomena of vigilante groups, such as the *Yan Sa Kai* in Zamfara and several Hausa community militias. These groups were first established for self-defense, but they have now been linked to retaliatory killings of Fulani villagers, creating new grievance cycles (Human Rights Watch, 2021; Danladi, 2026).

The humanitarian consequences are staggering. The United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs reports that by 2023,

bandit assaults have caused the displacement of over 1.4 million people in the North-West region alone (OCHA, 2023). This displacement has disrupted agricultural production, generating food insecurity that disproportionately affects women and children. Moreover, the closure of schools and healthcare facilities in conflict-affected areas has deepened long-term human development deficits that will fuel future cycles of deprivation and instability (Suleiman, 2026). More so, the cross-cutting social networks (market contacts, marriages, ceremonial co-participation) that social capital theorists describe as crucial barriers against escalating violence have also been undermined by the breakdown of intergroup harmony (Putnam, 2000; Varshney, 2002). The social foundation for peaceful coexistence diminishes when groups retreat into ethnic enclaves from mixed social settings, making future reconciliation increasingly challenging.

State Response and its Limitations

The Nigerian state's response to banditry between 2011 and 2025 has been characterised by inconsistency, capacity constraints, and strategic incoherence. While military operations like Operation Hadarin Daji, Operation Sharan Daji, and Operation Thunder Strike have been successful in weakening particular bandit groupings, they have not addressed the systemic factors that allow them to reappear. Although the Nigerian Air Force's airstrikes have been militarily successful in some cases, they have resulted in civilian losses that further alienate communities and encourage recruitment into bandit organizations (Amnesty International, 2025).

The amnesty experiments in Zamfara (2019-2021) and Katsina (2020) offers an alternate approach. Given the state's limited ability to employ force, proponents argue that negotiated disarmament is the only viable path toward peace. However, critics stress that amnesties without a proper disarmament, demobilization, and reintegration (DDR) frameworks can lead to bandits rearming and continuing attacks during peacetime (International Crisis Group, 2020).

Moreover, elite complicity too, has hampered responses from both the federal and state governments. The Ibrahim Gaidam administration in Zamfara, for instance, was particularly investigated, but claims of elite collusion span numerous regimes at both the state and federal levels. More so, a Human Rights Watch's 2021 report, cited specific events in which state personnel were implicated in providing arms to bandit groups, undermining the confidence of government security efforts in addressing the menace.

Recommendations

Deriving from the foregoing, this study makes the following suggestions based on the analysis presented above:

i. Structural Economic Reforms: To address the political cum economic roots of banditry in Northern Nigeria, significant investment in economic development in the North-West and North-Central regions is necessary. This includes targeted youth employment projects, vocational training, and support for agropastoral livelihoods. The Federal Government's Economic Sustainability Plan must be broadened, with an emphasis on banditry-affected areas.

ii. Community-Based Conflict Management: Rebuilding intergroup harmony requires funding community-based peace architecture—formal and informal processes that incorporate farmers, herders, religious leaders, women's associations, and youth groups into continuous discourse. Such institutions, like the National Peace Committee, should be devolved to local governments and given greater autonomy.

iii. Land and Grazing Policy Reform: One of the main structural causes of farmer-herder conflict in Nigeria has been the absence of a coherent national grazing strategy. Based on best practices from the Sahel and East Africa, the government should design and execute a land use system that permits both established agriculture and pastoralism.

iv. Accountability and Anti-Corruption Measures: The documented connection of political elites with the bandit economy must be thoroughly investigated and prosecuted. Anti-corruption agencies in Nigeria, such as the EFCC and ICPC, should be empowered to track down political beneficiaries of ransom payments and weapon sales.

v. Regional Cooperation: Given the transborder nature of banditry, with weapons originating in Libya, Mali, and Niger and illegal proceeds laundered over state borders, Nigeria should boost security cooperation with ECOWAS allies and the G5 Sahel Initiative.

vi. Security Sector Reform: Nigeria's security agencies must receive retraining in order to implement rules-of-engagement regulations and a community-focused approach to policing that will lower the number of civilian

casualties. In addition to military activities, the Nigeria Police Force's intelligence capabilities must be greatly expanded in the North-West.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that banditry in Nigeria is a complex phenomena with deep structural roots and far-reaching implications for intergroup harmony, rather than a simple law enforcement issue. Banditry has evolved into an organized criminal industry, methodically fragmenting northern Nigeria's multi-ethnic and multi-religious cohabitation patterns, driven by elite predation, youth unemployment, pastoral livelihood collapse, small arms proliferation, and governance failure. The implications for intergroup harmony are serious and potentially far-reaching. The weaponization of ethnic identity

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S/N	NAME	SEX	AGE	OCCUPATION	PLACE OF INTERVIEW	DATE OF INTERVIEW
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2	Mr. Danladi Farouq	M	45	Civil Servant	Virtual Interview	27/02/2026
3	Mr. Hassani Abubakar	M	60	Trader	Port Harcourt	30/03/2026
4	Mr. Usman Zakari	M	55	Trader	Port Harcourt	07/01/2026

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in the context of bandit raids, the growth of vigilante organizations, mass relocation, and the atrophy of cross-cutting social networks have resulted in a landscape of mutual suspicion and fear that will survive beyond the current security crisis. Rebuilding intergroup trust requires addressing not only security symptoms, but also the underlying economic, political, and governance causes that have made banditry a realistic employment alternative for tens of thousands of young Nigerians. Nigeria must choose between using military operations and amnesties to provide temporary relief and investing in long-term structural improvements to address the political economy of banditry. The evidence reviewed in this study strongly supports the latter approach.

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